

Tectonics

Supporting Information for

Provenance of the Mesozoic succession of Franz Josef Land (north-eastern Barents Sea): Paleogeographic and tectonic implications for the High Arctic

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Attachment 4 Geochemistry of magmatic pebbles.

Sample#	SiO2 %	Al2O3 %	TiO2 %	Fe2O3tot %	MnO %	MgO %	CaO %	Na2O %	K2O %	P2O5 %	LOI %	Summ %
Granites												
15-v15-25-2	74.02	13.77	0.3155	2.149	0.0337	0.458	0.6477	3.193	4.711	0.1065	0.714	100
15-v15-28-1	78.01	12.92	0.1347	1.371	<.01	0.2699	0.0692	4.973	1.3	<.05	0.996	100
15-v15-28-2	75.31	14.18	<.01	1.03	0.0149	<.1	0.749	4.13	3.932	<.05	0.582	100
15-v15-28-13	75.63	13.81	<.01	1.265	0.0172	0.1307	0.2276	1.864	5.853	<.05	1.1	99.94
15-v15-28-15	74.97	14.48	0.0398	1.321	0.0132	0.2411	1.423	5.421	1.71	<.05	0.508	100
15-v15-28-16	73.02	13.16	0.4667	4.068	0.1007	1.83	0.1741	5.561	0.229	0.0796	1.43	100
15-v15-28-23	75.95	13.28	0.1703	1.062	<.01	<.1	0.2116	2.5	5.653	0.0849	1.05	100
18-v15-34-8	73.79	14.64	0.1763	0.9506	<.01	<.1	<.01	4.912	4.772	<.05	0.72	100
Effusive												
15-v15-25-14	73.48	13.52	0.4661	4.036	0.1043	0.8785	0.0684	5.86	0.8858	0.0649	0.798	100
15-v15-28-4	75.1	12.43	0.2835	3.698	0.0681	1.005	0.2542	4.117	1.744	<.05	1.38	100
15-v15-28-14	84.07	8.553	0.4408	1.784	<.01	0.44	<.01	1.346	2.242	<.05	1.19	100
15-v15-28-18	77.26	11.8	0.4985	2.726	0.1022	0.9184	0.4998	4.059	0.4254	0.1952	1.61	100
15-v15-28-28	76.44	12.38	0.4582	1.471	<.01	<.1	0.0727	2.348	6.141	0.0976	0.474	99.95
18-v15-34-28	75.76	13.69	0.3213	1.001	<.01	0.1512	0.0418	3.785	4.372	0.067	0.88	100
18-v15-34-61	74.82	12.06	0.6211	3.623	0.0525	0.584	0.0597	2.563	4.681	<.05	0.876	100
18-v15-34-67	80.96	11.14	<.01	0.7662	<.01	<.1	0.2362	5.169	0.2381	<.05	1.57	100
18-v15-34-80	79.18	11.5	0.0147	1.641	0.0146	0.4858	0.0725	5.395	1.059	<.05	0.586	99.99
18-v15-34-105	80.46	10.44	0.0969	1.265	<.01	<.1	<.01	2.137	5.069	0.084	0.576	100
18-v15-35-45	77.14	11.34	0.144	1.501	<.01	0.1206	<.01	0.3304	8.888	<.05	0.634	100
18-v15-35-49	77.8	10.05	0.1562	3.061	<.01	<.1	<.01	1.226	6.552	<.05	1.23	100
18-v15-34-6	68.13	17.41	0.172	0.8691	<.01	0.1123	<.01	1.011	11.39	0.0774	0.798	99.99
18-v15-35-33	69.16	15.86	0.5698	1.486	<.01	<.1	0.1478	0.5347	10.79	0.1015	1.32	100

Sample#	Sc ppm	V ppm	Cr ppm	Co ppm	Ni ppm	Rb ppm	Sr ppm	Y ppm	Zr ppm	Nb ppm	Ba ppm	La ppm	Ce ppm	Pr ppm	Nd ppm	Sm ppm	Eu ppm	Gd ppm	Tb ppm	Dy ppm	Ho ppm	Er ppm	Tm ppm	Yb ppm	Lu ppm	Hf ppm	Ta ppm	Th ppm	U ppm	
Granites																														
15-v15-25-2	7.41	15.7	29.2	2.36	4.5	179	75	24.8	220	19.4	307	18.6	45.1	5.15	19	3.79	0.78	3.65	0.64	3.89	0.81	2.36	0.4	2.6	0.4	6.05	2.27	16.5	2.64	
15-v15-28-1	2.9	16.5	28.3	1.29	4.38	26.6	285	3.29	42.2	3.7	389	6.29	11.3	1.41	5.46	1.1	0.33	0.91	0.11	0.59	0.11	0.31	0.041	0.33	0.053	1.31	0.32	1.18	0.53	
15-v15-28-2	1.79	3.55	6.25	0.56	2.64	78.4	272	4.98	31.2	7.11	1250	2.24	4.01	0.51	2.08	0.52	0.18	0.52	0.1	0.69	0.17	0.54	0.079	0.53	0.077	1.06	0.44	1.9	0.41	
15-v15-28-13	3.43	5.92	9.25	0.94	4.3	260	80.5	26.5	37.3	13.2	487	8.26	17.1	2.07	7.91	2.52	0.4	3.08	0.62	3.89	0.77	2.35	0.34	2.21	0.31	1.71	1.63	6.47	2.21	
15-v15-28-15	1.91	6.51	8.75	1.36	3.34	31.2	239	5.19	62.4	9.46	439	1.37	2.66	0.31	1.15	0.3	0.15	0.4	0.097	0.74	0.18	0.61	0.11	0.75	0.11	2.81	2.13	2.67	3.54	
15-v15-28-16	3.63	28.1	8.16	2.14	3.12	2.11	36.4	4.5	112	2.91	37.2	0.82	2.23	0.31	1.47	0.42	0.059	0.46	0.09	0.58	0.15	0.54	0.094	0.74	0.14	3.1	<0.1	0.64	0.44	
15-v15-28-23	2.66	8.24	8.46	1.23	2.97	173	258	5.49	98.5	5.35	904	8.42	14.3	1.35	5.03	0.97	0.29	0.88	0.14	0.85	0.16	0.49	0.082	0.55	0.082	3.21	0.32	24.1	6.56	
18-v15-34-8	10.4	12.8	5.85	0.55	2.72	118	17.7	53.5	615	17.8	433	34	74.3	8.45	31.7	6.09	0.87	5.6	1.04	7.41	1.68	5.95	1.03	6.94	0.99	14.6	1.39	9.59	2.54	
Effusive																														
15-v15-25-14	11	7.41	24.7	2.55	12.1	8.9	29	36.1	158	4.63	66.8	3.82	9.49	1.11	5.23	1.42	0.35	2.32	0.51	4.38	1.2	4.18	0.7	4.8	0.76	4.66	0.33	2.05	0.92	
15-v15-28-4	4.99	11.1	11.1	3.07	9.14	24	56.3	21.9	183	5.73	409	4.86	11	1.44	6.12	1.48	0.27	1.88	0.37	2.85	0.72	2.63	0.48	3.43	0.53	5.48	0.41	4.21	1.42	
15-v15-28-14	5.48	21.1	17.9	3.5	7.83	67.6	21.6	18.9	174	11.2	415	33.8	70.1	7.95	29.5	5.29	1.13	4.36	0.65	3.45	0.66	1.85	0.27	1.7	0.23	4.5	0.81	7.53	0.82	
15-v15-28-18	8.24	14.7	4.63	5.55	10.4	5.87	217	19	81.7	1.51	77.9	9.1	21.2	2.7	12.7	3.21	0.83	2.98	0.46	2.96	0.61	2.16	0.34	2.31	0.37	2.58	<0.1	1.04	0.54	
15-v15-28-28	8.21	11.1	14.7	1.25	5.96	76.5	29.1	36.7	180	10.3	574	14.3	28.5	3.52	13.8	3.05	0.8	3.4	0.72	5.12	1.15	3.61	0.59	3.73	0.55	4.89	0.61	4.88	2.09	
18-v15-34-28	14.1	50	20.6	1.02	3.81	68.2	11	78.9	559	11.4	330	27.7	54.3	8.32	32.9	7.39	1.34	7.27	1.68	12	2.66	8.85	1.42	9.73	1.45	14.6	0.89	10.4	2.72	
18-v15-34-61	11.2	53	20.5	4.51	4.97	101	41.3	31.4	508	52.9	1350	27.8	64.4	6.72	26.3	5.26	0.94	4.46	0.76	4.58	1.03	3.97	0.71	5.44	0.89	13.1	4.27	11.2	3.3	
18-v15-34-67	2.18	9.88	8.74	<0.5	2.42	3.36	70.4	7.04	71.5	2.42	36.5	6.91	16.9	1.62	6.18	1.19	0.19	1	0.17	0.98	0.22	0.85	0.18	1.43	0.28	2.78	0.41	5.57	0.7	
18-v15-34-80	3.98	6.49	7.23	0.99	3.62	14.5	43.6	20	110	7.54	198	6.65	17.8	2.13	9.07	2.05	0.33	2	0.37	2.66	0.63	2.34	0.44	3.14	0.5	3.74	1.04	7.73	1.58	
18-v15-34-105	8.69	13.4	13.6	4.45	11.3	133	30.3	68.5	456	34.5	229	139	272	29.4	108	20.2	0.86	16.8	2.17	11.2	2.26	7.51	1.16	7.93	1.18	11.6	2.79	20.7	4.27	
18-v15-35-45	2.18	25	14.6	1.57	6.26	96.1	8.9	4.64	89.7	4.22	215	9.82	21.2	2.12	8.03	1.38	0.28	1.13	0.15	0.84	0.13	0.51	0.066	0.49	0.078	2.62	0.4	2.64	0.94	
18-v15-35-49	13.3	16.7	14.6	4.9	13.9	176	24.2	128	993	69.6	170	56.2	158	14.3	57	12.1	0.58	13	2.73	19.2	4.15	12.9	1.94	13	2.16	25	5.63	20.5	4.39	
18-v15-34-6	6.04	24.9	12.9	1.35	4.02	183	25.1	21.8	118	6.33	1460	16.5	40	4.6	18.8	3.98	1.05	3.49	0.55	3.45	0.74	2.35	0.38	2.41	0.36	3.51	0.52	5.6	1.18	
18-v15-35-33	8.99	34.5	18	3.61	23.6	201	79.5	32.5	437	18.8	584	66	90.8	12	43.6	7.36	1.47	5.89	0.95	5.54	1.14	3.63	0.6	4.12	0.73	11.2	1.46	9.98	2.02	
	0.2	2.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	2	1	0.1	0.5	0.5	3	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.005	0.005	0.01	0.005	0.01	0.005	0.01	0.005	0.01	0.005	0.01	0.1	0.1	0.1	